

EFFECTIVENESS OF KINESIOTHERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH OSTEOCHONDROSIS**Khrustalova I.,
Kamyshna I***I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University***ABSTRACT**

In modern conditions, due to such provoking factors as sedentary lifestyle, flat feet, obesity, increased load on the spine, natural aging processes, smoking, autoimmune diseases and other factors, the number of people facing a disease such as osteochondrosis of the spine is growing. In 80% of cases, back pain is associated with lumbosacral osteochondrosis. This question requires special attention from medical workers and specialists of rehabilitation centers, since osteochondrosis becomes much younger, and this requires the improvement of prevention, treatment and rehabilitation measures for this disease.

Keywords: kinesiotherapy, osteochondrosis, rehabilitation, integrated approach, lumbar spine.

Formulation of the problem. The main task in the rehabilitation of osteochondrosis is the prevention of the disease and improvement of the patient's quality of life. The latest scientific studies confirm the importance of starting treatment and rehabilitation measures in the early stage of osteochondrosis of the spine. This helps to avoid complications such as spinal hernias, gynecological problems in women and impotence and chronic prostatitis in men, as well as problems with defecation and urination. Therefore, it is important to provide optimal conditions for rehabilitation, starting it immediately after the diagnosis of osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral spine.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Theoretical and practical studies of kinesiotherapy were carried out by the following specialists: Dovgiy I.L., Kovalenko O.E., Kormiltsev, V.V., Korkushko O.O., Lazareva E.B., Macheret E.L., Mukhin V.M., Tsybalyuk V.I. and other.

Isolation of unresolved aspects of the problem. To date, the effectiveness of various methods of kinesiotherapy for osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral spine at the non-acute stage of the disease is poorly studied. According to research results, kinesiotherapy, together with orthopedic, medicinal and physiotherapeutic methods of rehabilitation, has a positive effect on the treatment of spinal diseases of various degrees of severity.

The purpose of the article is to evaluate the effectiveness of using a rehabilitation complex, which includes kinesiotherapy with kinesotaping, in the treatment and rehabilitation of patients with osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral spine.

Presenting main material. Under the influence of various factors, the bone tissue of the vertebrae and the cartilage tissue lose their strength, which leads to a decrease in the distance between the vertebrae of the spinal column. Decreased tissue elasticity is the main cause of disc deformation, which can cause pinched nerve endings and cause pain. According to the International Classification of Diseases (ICD), osteochondrosis belongs to the group of diseases of the musculoskeletal system, mainly the spine. According to MKX-10, which is in the public domain of WHO, the osteochondrosis code is M-42. Spine diseases are one of the

most common pathologies that can affect people of any age. More than 20% of people experience chronic back pain, and 70% have problems with their spine at least once. Complaints about pain in the spine are particularly common. According to the World Health Organization, osteochondrosis is the third most common disease, after cardiovascular and oncological diseases. From 40 to 90% of the world's population of various age groups suffers from osteochondrosis.

In Ukraine, the number of patients with osteochondrosis is 144 per 10,000 population, including disabled people – 3 per 10,000 population. Many patients with this diagnosis are prescribed operations. However, after operations, a significant number of such patients become disabled, so diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation and prevention of osteochondrosis are of great importance.

Osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral region is characterized by a systemic lesion of cartilage tissue of the degenerative-dystrophic type with the inclusion of articular, bone, muscle, ligament and other structures of this area of the spine. The term “degenerative” means that the disease is based on metabolic disorders, activity and nutrition of various spinal systems without an infectious and inflammatory component. There are more than 10 theories of the development of osteochondrosis, including vascular, involutional, hormonal, infectious, rheumatoid, autoimmune, traumatic, abnormal development of the spine and others.

Usually, osteochondrosis is preceded by damage to the intervertebral discs, which consist of the nucleus pulposus, which is located in the center of the disc and gives it elasticity, and the fibrous ring. Deterioration of the supply of these discs leads to the destruction of their structure.

The development of osteochondrosis begins with damage to the nucleus pulposus of the intervertebral disc: first it loses moisture, and then its central position shifts. The nucleus can separate into separate segments and disintegrate, causing the annulus fibrosus to become less elastic, thinner, and softened, and cracks may appear on it. In the case of cracks in the fibrous ring, it can tear, and then partially or completely the core goes beyond the disc, forming a herniated disc.

Degenerative changes in the disc lead to a change in the height of the discs and, accordingly, the distance

between adjacent vertebrae, which gradually decreases. During increased movement or load on the spine, displacement of the vertebral bodies is possible, which leads to instability of the intervertebral discs.

Reverse development of structural changes in the spine is almost impossible, but reducing these changes is a real task. If treatment, rehabilitation and prevention are not carried out, the changes will progress and the pain will become more intense.

With degenerative-dystrophic changes of the intervertebral discs, there is a decrease in the elasticity of the disc and a deterioration in the functions of the spine, such as a decrease in resistance to physical exertion, limitation of the range of motion in the spine, the occurrence of pain, which affects the psycho-emotional state and reduces work capacity, and in 25% of cases leads to disability .

Pain can affect various structures of the spine, including autonomic ligaments, joints, spinal roots of nerve endings, and can cause irradiation to internal organs, upper and lower extremities, contributing to the development of shingles.

There are several theories regarding the origin of osteochondrosis, such as metabolic disorders, endocrine disorders, muscle disorders, and others. This indicates that the causes of this disease are not yet fully understood and require additional research.

The causes of osteochondrosis can be classified as follows:

Endogenous (internal):

- disorders of the development of the spine in the mother's womb.
- age-related changes in cartilage tissue.
- hereditary predisposition to osteochondrosis.
- metabolic disorders, in particular calcium and phosphorus.
- body intoxication.
- nervous tension and stress.
- hormonal changes, such as pregnancy or menopause.
- severe somatic diseases.
- autoimmune diseases of the connective tissue of the spine.

Exogenous (external):

- incorrect distribution of the load on the spine.
- injuries and damage to the spine, both professional and domestic.
- stooping and incorrect posture.
- weakness of the back muscles and lateral (s-shaped) curvature of the spine.
- deficiency of trace elements and vitamins (magnesium, manganese, zinc and vitamin d).
- using uncomfortable mattresses and pillows for sleeping.

Factors associated with increased load on the spine:

- excess weight.
- heavy physical exertion, especially heavy lifting.
- working posture, standing or sitting.
- wearing uncomfortable shoes and high heels, as well as unevenly distributed weight of the bag on the shoulders.
- incorrect posture.

- insufficiently developed muscular corset of the spine, which is the result of a sedentary lifestyle.
- congenital and acquired spinal deformities.
- flat feet.

Until recently, osteochondrosis was considered as a disease that occurs mainly in the elderly due to age-related changes in the mobility and elasticity of the vertebrae and discs. However, now this problem is becoming relevant for people over 30 years of age, and it is becoming an important object of research and treatment.

There are several widespread classifications of types of osteochondrosis, described below:

1. Classification based on the display of degenerative changes in the structural elements of the vertebrae:

- pathological processes inside the intervertebral disc, known as chondrosis. The nucleus pulposus, located in the center, can shift and lead to fissures through which nerve endings are irritated.

- the stage of instability, where changes in the middle of the disc disrupt the fixation of the vertebrae relative to each other, which leads to the formation of reflex and compression syndromes.

- the formation of a hernia, where the protrusion leads to the displacement of the intervertebral discs, compresses the vascular-nerve bundles and irritates the roots of the spinal nerves.

- the formation of fibrosis, when the surfaces of the vertebrae fit tightly due to the displacement of the intervertebral discs, which leads to the formation of bone growths.

2. Clinical stages of osteochondrosis according to the severity of the pain syndrome:

- mild pains that usually do not cause serious attention and may disappear after a short rest.

- moderate pain with partial restriction of activity caused by the destruction of the fibrous ring and restriction of the intervertebral space.

- pronounced pain syndrome, which can be accompanied by greater deformation of the fibrous ring and the formation of intervertebral hernias.

- sharp pains, intense pain that cannot be relieved by painkillers. At this stage, paralysis of the limbs and disruption of internal organs may occur, limiting daily activities.

3. Classification by localization of the pathological process:

- cervical department.

- chest section.

- lumbar department.

- lumbosacral department.

4. Classification according to the dynamics of the disease:

- acute form (up to 4 weeks).

- subacute form (from 4 weeks to 3 months).

The static and dynamic apparatus of the spine consists of abdominal muscles, trunk, muscles connecting the trunk and limbs, as well as long and short back muscles [2]. To ensure the normal functioning of the spine, it is necessary to constantly maintain the physiological tone of the muscles and ligaments [2]. The muscles and ligaments of the spine perform several interrelated

functions, the main of which is mechanical stability, which provides the physiological mechanism of movement. Due to the elastic properties of the ligaments, they act as a passive frame of the spine, consuming minimal energy, while muscles perform the same function, but with high energy consumption [7].

L. F. Vasiliev distinguishes between sanogenetic and pathogenetic mechanisms of biomechanical changes in the musculoskeletal system. The main mechanism of formation of sanogenic changes is functional blocks as a sanogenic reaction of the body. They can be detected in the following situations:

1) dislocation of the nucleus pulposus, accompanied by increased afferentation of the fibrous ring, excessive mobility of the vertebral motor segment (CRS), traumatization of the nerve root and adjacent structures.

2) dynamic or static overload of the HRS, which requires additional fixation.

3) long-term hypermobility in the neighboring CRS leads to the formation of instability at this level, which requires the formation of a compensatory functional unit for additional fixation.

The causes of the formation of pathogenic changes in biomechanics include:

1) long-term restriction of movement in the case of functional block of CRS, which leads to a decrease in the endogenous rhythm of CRS, accompanied by the formation of functional weakness in the muscles associated with the functional block of muscle genesis, articular genesis and in muscles innervated by the roots of the spinal cord of the brain, which come out of the intervertebral openings at the level of the CRS, which has a functional block.

2) functional blocks accompanied by asymmetry of the location of the vertebrae lead to changes in the tension of the ligamentous apparatus and the dura mater of adjacent structures, which is manifested by the formation of a ligament imbalance and torsion of the dura mater at this level.

One of the main manifestations of osteochondrosis (OS) is a feeling of pain and discomfort in the spine [2]. Depending on the stage of degenerative changes in the vertebrae and intervertebral discs, pain can be permanent or temporary, appearing and disappearing during physical exertion.

Different localizations cause various symptoms of OX:

- In the cervical region, there is pain in the neck, hands, restriction of movement, numbness of the fingers, headache, throbbing headache and other manifestations [3].

- Acute or aching pain in the back, feeling of a "peg in the chest", pain in the heart and other internal organs, difficulty breathing may occur in the thoracic region.

- In the lumbar region, there may be pain in the lower back, sacrum and legs, increase during movements, shooting in the lower back during physical exertion, numbness of the lower limbs and various disorders of the genitourinary organs [3].

During the period of remission, the pain may not be so pronounced and occur only in the presence of provoking factors, such as physical exertion or an uncomfortable position.

In addition to pain and numbness in the legs, individuals with OX may experience genital disorders, increased fatigue, cold hands and feet, stiffness, locking, and weakness of the joints, as well as the inability to fully straighten the affected limb [4].

There are several options for the nature of the pain:

- local pain in the lower back and sacrum (lumbago, lumbago).

- dull, aching pain in the lower back and deep tissues in the area of the hip, knee and ankle joints – sclerotomy pain (lumboischialgia).

- sharp pain that "shoots" from the lower back to the buttock area and down the leg to the fingers along the course of the affected root – radicular pain (sciatica) [4].

Anamnesis analysis and physical examination are important in the diagnosis of OC. The clinical picture may depend on such factors as etiological factors, age, sex, duration of pain, pathophysiological mechanisms, as well as psychological and social status [4].

When examining the patient, it is important to take into account his position, the presence of tension in the paravertebral muscles and painful points on the periphery, which can form a pain syndrome [5]. The tension of the spinal roots can cause acute pain, the localization of which has important diagnostic value.

Treatment of osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral spine is determined by the localization of the pathological process, the nature of clinical syndromes (reflex, compressive root, compressive vascular, spinal syndromes), the stage of the disease, and the severity of the pain syndrome [6]. There are various methods of treatment, such as medication, conservative (exercise, physical therapy, massage, medical diet, etc.) and operative (surgical intervention in severe cases). Drug treatment is mainly aimed at reducing the pain syndrome, while rehabilitation methods can be more effective and have a long-lasting effect [7].

Treatment should begin with changing the patient's lifestyle. For the correct distribution of the load on the spine, it is recommended to choose an orthopedic mattress and pillow, to avoid excessive physical exertion. The main goals of rehabilitation for osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral spine are relief of pain, stabilization of the patient's condition, improvement of self-care, restoration of biomechanics and mobility of the spine, improvement of muscle tone.

In the rehabilitation process, it is important to consider various factors, such as the stage of the disease and the recovery period. Rehabilitation methods may include physical therapy, physical therapy, massage, kinesoteaping, gentle methods of manual therapy, physiotherapeutic procedures (acupuncture, vacuum therapy, laser therapy, pharmacopuncture, dry stretching, magnetopuncture, water procedures) and others.

Physical therapy is one of the important elements of treatment, but it is necessary to choose gentle exercises and avoid overloading the muscles and spine. Exercises are aimed at improving muscle tone, forming a

muscular corset, developing joints and muscles, and improving nutrition.

Massage is an effective method of treatment aimed at increasing the tone and elasticity of the back muscles, improving blood circulation and lymphatic drainage. Manual massage can include various techniques, such as classic, segmental-reflex, periosteal, connective tissue and point.

Rehabilitation for osteochondrosis varies from the period of debut to complete remission, including increased motor activity, stabilization and strengthening of the muscle corset. Correctly conducted rehabilitation plays a key role in restoring health, eliminating pain and improving the patient's quality of life.

You can also use other types of massage, such as vacuum massage, stone massage, honey massage, Thai massage, acupuncture massage, massage with essential oils and herbal bags. In addition, kinesio taping can be used. This method, developed by the Japanese doctor Kenzo Kashi in 1973, helps to improve blood circulation, reduce swelling and pain, and also helps to increase the mobility of the spine. The method of application involves cutting a tape in the shape of a "V", which is glued along the spine to improve various aspects of the body's physiology.

Kinesio taping has almost no contraindications, but its effect on the body should be taken into account in certain conditions, such as diabetes, cancer, thrombosis, heart failure, reflux disease, etc.

The selected rehabilitation program has its advantages, such as the exclusion of uncontrolled effects on the body, taking into account the body's natural capabilities for self-regulation and recovery, the absence of pain, medications and overloads. It is marked by improvement of health, reduction of pain sensations and improvement of sleep quality after the first classes.

Kinesio taping is an auxiliary method of treating osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral spine, and the number of sessions is determined individually, usually at least 6 times until full recovery of functions.

Manual therapy, or "hands treatment", includes manipulations to treat the spine and joints, restore movement and remove joint blocks. Although manual therapy for osteochondrosis does not have scientific evidence, patients note its effectiveness, and research continues.

Physiotherapy procedures, such as pulsed and direct currents, magnetic field, ultrasound, laser therapy and others, are more effective and safer compared to drug treatment. They are aimed at improving trophic, microcirculation and motor function of tissues.

Physiotherapy includes reflexology, which has a low number of contraindications and high efficiency, does not cause side effects and is well tolerated by patients.

Water treatment, in particular with the help of oxygen and hydrogen sulfide baths, is a popular method of preventing osteochondrosis of the spine in sanatoriums. The course of baths consists of 10-12 procedures, which are prescribed to patients every other day. Performing physical exercises in water helps to strengthen the muscle corset, stretch the spine and increase its mobility, and this method can be used in the initial stages

of the disease. Magnetic therapy helps to reduce the pain syndrome by performing 10 procedures of 20 minutes on the affected area of the spine.

Physiotherapy, or "movement therapy", is an effective method of rehabilitation based on the movements of muscles and joints. It can be used for most diseases of the musculoskeletal system, having few contraindications and high clinical efficiency. It is recommended to start it immediately after stabilization of the patient's condition. Physiotherapy is aimed at restoring motor function, reducing the risk of complications and preserving physical ability. It is used for osteochondrosis, protrusions of intervertebral discs, instability between vertebrae, curvature of the spine, arthrosis and other diseases. Contraindications include pain during exercise, oncological diseases of the spine and joints, acute injuries, spinal operations, etc. The purpose of physical exercises is individual for each patient, taking into account the anamnesis and physiological characteristics. Physiotherapy can be active or passive, using different movements and devices.

Conclusions. Osteochondrosis of the spine is a multifactorial disease that is not associated with inflammatory processes and has a degenerative-dystrophic nature. In people over 30 years of age, one in four suffers from radiculopathy, which is one of the manifestations of osteochondrosis. Rehabilitation programs for patients with osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral spine using kinesiotherapy methods were the object of analysis. The important role of physical therapy in solving the problem of comprehensive improvement of the health status of patients with osteochondrosis of the lumbosacral spine has been confirmed. A significant reduction in pain, improvement in spinal mobility, and improvement in quality of life were noted in patients who were treated with a rehabilitation complex, including physical therapy with kinesio taping, and maintenance of effectiveness for up to 6 months after rehabilitation measures. The rehabilitation methods used in this study are aimed at reducing pain, increasing range of motion, and preventing further progression of this pathology. The rehabilitation complex, including physical therapy with kinesio taping, reliably ($p < 0.05$) contributed to the improvement of the quality of life.

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